

Lifecycle Metric Integration in Lamination Parameters Design Space for Structural Optimisation of Composite Structures

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The importance of light-weighting in aviation

The number of decommissioned aircraft

New commercial aircraft 2022

- Airbus: 661
- Boeing: 542

Predicted growth per annum 4.3% for the next 20 years [2]

Estimated cumulative number of aircraft to be recycled between now and the year 2043 based on these numbers:

22,190 ✈️

(assuming an average life span of 30 years)

Current state of the art at end-of-life aircraft:

- ±10 weeks to process a decommissioned aircraft
- Only a limited number of parts is reused / recycled
- Most of the airframe is scrapped

The energy transition and the growing number of decommissioned aircraft require that the paradigm that weight reduction automatically leads to better lifecycle performance of composite aircraft structures should be revisited.

Presentation Contents

1. Variable stiffness laminate design
2. Life cycle metrics as a design constraint
3. Concept study
4. Discussion and outlook

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Variable Stiffness Laminate Design

Using structural optimisation to compensate for
a reduction in mechanical properties

Variable Stiffness Laminate Design

Using in plane load redistribution to improve mechanical performance

Performance maximisation → Weight minimisation

02

Life Cycle Metrics

Integration in Lamination Parameter space

Using lamination parameters

$$(V_1^A, V_2^A, V_3^A, V_4^A) = \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} (\cos 2\theta, \sin 2\theta, \cos 4\theta, \sin 4\theta) d\bar{z}$$

$$(V_1^B, V_2^B, V_3^B, V_4^B) = 4 \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \bar{z} (\cos 2\theta, \sin 2\theta, \cos 4\theta, \sin 4\theta) d\bar{z}$$

$$(V_1^D, V_2^D, V_3^D, V_4^D) = 12 \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \bar{z}^2 (\cos 2\theta, \sin 2\theta, \cos 4\theta, \sin 4\theta) d\bar{z}$$

a) Carbon/PEEK (AS4) - Tension

b) Carbon/Epoxy (IM6) - Compression

c) Boron/Epoxy (B5.6) - Compression

03

Demonstration of Concept

Case study: simply supported uniaxially compressed plate

Simply supported uniaxially compressed plate

$$E_{b_C} = w_{f_{PM}} \cdot E_{b_{PM}} + w_{f_{RF}} \cdot E_{b_{RF}}$$

$$w_{f_{PM}} = \frac{m_{PM}}{m_{RF} + m_{PM}}$$

$$w_{f_{RF}} = \frac{m_{RF}}{m_{RF} + m_{PM}}$$

$$E_C = E^{rw}_C + E^m_C = E_{b_C} \cdot (m_{RF} + m_{PM}) + SEC_C \cdot (m_{RF} + m_{PM})$$

$$SEC_{SFVS} = SEC_{process} * n_{regions}^{1/a}$$

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	E_{b_C} [MJ/kg]	SEC_C [MJ/kg]	w_{RF} [%]	w_{PM} [%]	E [MJ/kg]
Aluminium	70.1	324	-	38.6	-	-	230 / 26.7*
Composite A	30.2	276	392	600	40	60	-
Composite B	21.2	115	184.8	79	40	60	-

- E_{b_C} : embodied energy of the composite (MJ/kg);
- $w_{f_{PM}}$: weight fraction of polymer matrix (-);
- $E_{b_{PM}}$: embodied energy of the polymer matrix (MJ/kg);
- $w_{f_{RF}}$: weight fraction of reinforcement (-);
- $E_{b_{RF}}$: embodied energy of the reinforcement (MJ/kg);
- m_{PM} : mass of the polymer matrix (kg);
- m_{RF} : mass of the reinforcement (kg);
- E_C : overall energy of the composite component (MJ);
- E^{rw}_C : energy embedded in the composite raw materials (MJ);
- E^m_C : energy needed to manufacture a composite component (MJ);
- SEC_C : specific energy consumption of the manufacturing process (MJ/kg).

All values presented in this work are for demonstration purposes only.

Straight-Fibre Variable Stiffness Laminates

Continuous fibre angle variation

Multi-patch laminate

Straight-Fibre Variable Stiffness Laminate

SFVS

Results

Baseline aluminum panel, 2.0mm thick

Buckling load [kN]	Weight [kg]	E [MJ]
5.5351	1.296	298.08 / 34.99*

Composite A: Carbon fibre reinforced PEEK
Laser assisted AFP
Autoclave

Number of design regions [-]	Weight [kg]	E [MJ]			
		a = 2	a = 4	a = 6	a = 8
1	1.142	1133.00	1133.00	1133.00	1133.00
9	0.999	2190.03	1429.94	1256.22	1180.58
25	0.904	3065.95	1567.00	1281.68	1165.29
49	0.880	4040.53	1741.73	1354.84	1203.67
81	0.856	4960.45	1877.30	1404.59	1225.75
121	0.844	5900.10	2009.99	1456.79	1252.84
225	0.842	7909.80	2287.80	1577.01	1325.28

Composite B: Glass fibre reinforced PEEK
Hand lay-up
Thermo forming

Number of design regions [-]	Weight [kg]	E [MJ]			
		a = 2	a = 4	a = 6	a = 8
1	1.593	420.22	420.22	420.22	420.22
9	1.393	587.77	448.18	416.28	402.39
25	1.261	730.93	455.66	403.27	381.89
49	1.227	905.45	483.30	412.25	384.49
81	1.194	1070.02	503.83	417.03	384.19
121	1.177	1240.24	525.86	424.27	386.82
225	1.174	1609.99	577.57	447.05	400.82

$$SEC_{SFVS} = SEC_{process} * n_{regions}^{1/a}$$

$$[\pm\theta_1/\pm\theta_2/\pm\theta_3/\pm\theta_4/\pm\theta_5/\pm\theta_6/\pm\theta_7/\pm\theta_8]_s$$

04

Discussion and Outlook

Changing the paradigm

Discussion

- All values presented in this work are for demonstration purposes only
- The work presented is a preliminary study in this direction
- This study is limited to energy required for a composite component
- The energy required to manufacture the aluminium plate is lower than for either composite material
- The energy required to manufacture the composite B panel is roughly a third of that required for the composite A panel
- The results for composite B show that it should be possible to reduce the overall energy of a composite component by means of structural optimisation
- In follow-up work a full optimisation for a number of materials and production processes will be performed

The **choice** of **composite** aircraft parts over **aluminium** aircraft parts is to be considered carefully should the **life cycle impact of light-weighting** become less dominant in the future

Thank you for your attention

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